

Understanding the Determinant Factors of Digital Transformation for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises: Post Pandemic Context

Arief Rahman

arief.rahman@uii.ac.id

Andrej Privara

andrej.privara@euba.sk

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the critical factors that influence Digital Transformation (DT) among Indonesian Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), especially in the post-pandemic context. Data were collected through online survey from 341 respondents. The study applied Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) methods for the analysis. The findings show that the determinants of DT are IS capacity, competitive pressure, and government support, while perceived benefits and complexity are weaker influencing factors. The drivers work differentially according to the size of the enterprise: in micro-enterprises, it is more of an external pressure and technological capabilities, while in small businesses, it is driven by internal management support. No variables were significantly influential in medium-scaled enterprises; therefore, further research is required. It also underlines the challenges in low digital skills, financial constraints, and the general allergy to change. The paper underscores how multidimensional efforts toward DT dimensions—technological readiness, external pressures, and supportive policies—are urgent to improve MSME competitiveness, resilience, and sustainability.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, MSMEs, DT Factors, Post-Pandemic, Indonesia

JEL codes: O32, O33, M15

1. Introduction

In Indonesia, MSMEs are significantly contributing to the national economy by creating employment opportunities, reducing poverty, and enhancing national income (Tambunan, 2019). Moreover, MSMEs promote innovation and create new opportunities for entrepreneurship, thus contributing to the diversification of a country's economy (Kussudyarsana, 2023). In addition, the MSMEs assist in regional development since they significantly distribute the national income into different provinces, reducing regional gaps (Nursini, 2020). Understanding the pivotal role of the MSMEs in the Indonesian economy, the government has developed a number of policies, such as financing for the development of enterprises, capacity building, and simplification of the regulatory framework for efficient functioning of MSMEs (Latianingsih and et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, the importance of DT to MSMEs is emphasized by the fact that competitiveness, resilience and sustainable development in a rapidly dynamic environment is inevitable. Additionally, the adaptation of digital technologies allows MSMEs to optimize processes and improve productivity, creating new opportunities by innovation, and allowing them to adopt to the dynamic market needs (Ben-Zvi and Luftman, 2022). Importantly, DT improves the resilience of MSMEs to respond and adopt swiftly to the disruption in the markets or shocks, observed during the crises including the COVID-19 pandemic where the online

platforms were the only major way for sustaining MSMEs (Uvarova and Pobol, 2021). Therefore, the DT is not an option for MSMEs but a need in the contemporary business environment, enabling them to grow, compete effectively and be sustainable.

The aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic further accelerates the urgency and need of DT for MSMEs. The pandemic acted a forcing function, highlighting how essential it is for companies to establish strategies which support and ensure business continuity through the DT. This trend further accelerated when digitally transformed firms continued to operate during the economic shocks and disruption and were able to size new opportunities and survive during the crisis (Battistoni, 2023). When the economies are recovering back or developing, digitalization continues to be crucial for MSMEs sustainability and competitiveness (Kuczevska & et al., 2023). The DT helps in determining how MSMEs can improve their business management and operations, growth, and efficiency, thus allowing them to meet customers' changing demands and market requirements (Matt & Rauch, 2020). Also, DT enables remote working theme, which have proven to be a crucial in managing ongoing business operations and safeguarding employees' health during the COVID-19 outbreak. Being equipped by digital technologies such as e-commerce platforms, online marketing, online business operations, data analytics for Marketing and Sales, and remote operations will be not only enabled MSMEs to survive but grow in the post covid-19 (Ben-Zvi and Luftman, 2022). Thus, the post COVID-19 indicates on the need for effective strategy to DT of MSMEs, enhancing the resilience and adaptability for future changes and contributing to MSMEs growth.

The DT has many advantages for MSMEs, but it also has its challenges. On the positive impact, the adoption of digital technologies helps the MSMEs to streamline their operation more effectively and extend it to a larger number of markets. Due to DT, MSMEs are able to enhance customer communication, gain deeper insights into the customers' needs and dressing them effectively, enhancing customer satisfaction. In addition to this, DT empowers the MSMEs with the right knowledge through using relevant data to support their decision making and strategic developments. DT also facilitates innovation, as result the MSMEs can come up with new products or services, obtaining market power and adjusting according to needs of the customers (Straková & et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the implementation of DT in MSMEs also have certain challenges, such as insufficient funding, lack of digital proficiency, data protection, and organizational resistance to DT (Rupeika-Apoga & Petrovska, 2022). Moreover, it poses challenges on the intricate nature of digital technologies and the identification of the most relevant and needed DT for MSMEs. However, the benefits of the implementation of the DT outweigh the challenges, it is important for the MSMEs to implement the measures to remain competitive, efficient, and resilient.

The main purpose of this research is to explore the important factors affecting the DT among MSMEs in Indonesia, covering the driver such as competitive pressure, managerial support, IS infrastructure, and government support, and complexity of DT. This research is relevant because MSMEs plays an important role in creating employment opportunities, reducing poverty, and driving regional development in Indonesian. Knowledge on these factors is imperative for increasing efficiency, innovativeness as well as effectiveness within the operations of the MSMEs, particularly after COVID-19. The paper also stresses on the importance of systematic DT for MSMEs to continue operating and compete effectively in worldwide markets, as evidenced by their testimonies throughout the COVID-19 outbreak and contributes to making policymakers and business managers aware of strategies that will assist them to implement DT successfully. The paper is structured as literature review, methodology, result, discussion, and conclusion.

RQ: *What are the key factors that influence an MSME to implement DT in Indonesia?*

2. Literature Review

DT means a significant change in organizations with the application of digital technologies in different aspects to improve the performance, optimize customers' satisfaction and create new and innovative solutions. This strategic adoption is as a result of such technologies as the Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), big data, and Internet of Things (IoT) which helps organizations to design and improve organizational processes.

The need for DT is further highlighted by the fact that DT is said to enhance the performance and competitiveness of an organization; digitally matured firms are estimated to be 26% more profitable than firms that have not been mature (Wroblewski, 2018). Nonetheless, DT implementation processes counters challenges such as resistance against changes by organizational structures and employees, significant skill gaps among employees, and security and privacy of the data (Rupeika-Apoga & Petrovska, 2022). While leadership commitment, customer orientation, and effective utilization of agile approaches are vital prerequisites for the implementation of DT projects (Ismael, 2022). Additionally, industry specific DT depicts its specific opportunities and challenges, for example IoT and AI enhance supply chains in the manufacturing industry, patient care is enhanced through telemedicine and electronic records (Straková & et al., 2022). Thus, when it comes to dealing with the complexity of DT, the most optimal strategy comprises of a comprehensive approach which integrate technological adaptation, organizational culture, nurturing of skills, and adequate security measures to obtain a more competitive advantage and satisfying the increasing customer demands in the digital era.

Digitalization which refers to the embedding of digital technologies throughout organisational structures is a phenomenon that is revolutionizing global industries at a very fast rate. The latest studies by Sarkar and Shankar (2021) elucidate its transitive influence, ranging from the automation of processes to data-driven decision, leading to such improvement of performance, innovation, and competitive advantage. Additionally, digitalization is essential for MSMEs development, as it helps them build operational competitive advantages and improve their business sustainability. MSMEs paly a very crucial role in the economy of Indonesia, but they have major issues like inadequate capital, and compliance issues (Tambunan, 2019). It became a noticeable trend in Indonesia, since the government decided to modernize and promotes the digital economy initiative. Further, the DT of MSMEs in Indonesia is crucial to survive in a digitally dynamic environment, and the COVID-19 pandemic became an awakening to the need for digital integration, since conventional approaches significantly halted MSMEs operation during the pandemic and impacted the survival of business with negligible levels of digitization (Sunoko & et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, the challenges such as digital competencies of SME owners, limited funds to invest in recent technology, Fragmented digital literacy, skill gap, cybersecurity and privacy issues, and unequal distribution of the digital infrastructure are the main challenges and hurdle. Nonetheless, there is also higher potential and opportunities that can be utilized through digital literacy initiative by government, development of a viable e-business support strategy, establishing of a mechanism for cooperation and sharing experiences among MSMEs. Stressing on digitalisation as a competitive necessity will enable the Indonesian MSMEs to improve productivity, introduce new services and products, thereby fostering their growth in the long run (Sunoko & et al., 2022). Therefore, to realise the huge opportunity that accrues to the digital technologies, Indonesia needs to effectively respond to the above challenges and create a conducive environment for the MSMEs.

DT in MSMEs is gradually being placed as one of the key factors of competitiveness, innovation and sustainability that radically alters the processes of companies 'functioning and their relations with customers (Khurana & et al., 2022). It is obvious that effective management and managers play a central role in the leading of DT process by strong commitment of the leadership, clear vision, long term strategy, and management of resources. In Indonesia, the degree of managerial consciousness and positive approaches towards DT significantly influence the level of DT adaptation. However, managers experience challenges, such as lack of financial resources, lack of digital skills, and resistance to change. These challenges are further magnified by lack of infrastructural development and inefficient regulatory frameworks, while measures to effective management of DT are acquiring and developing human resources in the IT sphere, encouraging the dissemination of innovative ideas, and utilizing government incentives (Aidi & et al., 2022). The empirical literature indicates on the positive impact of DT and resilience of MSMEs, evident during economic disruption, for example COVID-19 in Indonesia (Sunoko & et al., 2022). Additionally, those managers who effectively managed DT and applied data analytics and digital marketing, their performance leads to large competitive advantage in the market. Indonesian experience shows diverse circumstances in the adaptation of e-commerce; some small retail companies have incorporated e-commerce for market access enlargement while digital supply chain management for manufacturing MSMEs is also useful for operational efficiency (Latianingsih and etal., 2022). Such examples prove the importance of the manager's leadership in promoting the DT and handling the challenges in the implementation of digitization. Thus, effective management of DT, supportive government policies, investments in digital skills, and a culture of innovation are the core of the succeeding DT for development.

The Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework, developed by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990), is widely used to study technology adoption within organizations by examining three contexts: such as: technological, organizational and environmental factors. The technological context includes perceived benefits, compatibility and perceived complexity of the related technologies that affects the adoption decision. The organizational context includes factors such as size and structure of firms, management, and resources; proportionately, large firms are more tractable to adopt newer technologies because they are apt to bear risks and invest in innovations. Some of the challenges that MSMEs encountering includes limited financial and human capital. While external factors such as labour market dynamics, regulatory framework, and competitiveness pressure are considered as environmental challenges forcing firms to adopt innovative technologies and maintain their maker share (Arapaci & et al., 2012). The TOE framework has been used in different fields or settings such as e-commerce context, cloud computing, and ERP systems context, showing its explaining power of modelling technology adoption. However, it has some drawbacks that include its broad categorization, consequently, not take adequate account of the unique industry context or the changing progress made in the industrial sector and technologies (Wang & et al., 2010). Despite of these challenges the TOE framework can be a useful tool to comprehend and provide technological adaptation, particularly in the industrial sector.

Figure 1. Technology-Organization-Environment Framework

Source: Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990)

3. Methodology and Data

The primary sources of data utilized in this study is based on online surveys to efficiently reach out to a diverse population and conduct comprehensive interviews to elicit individualized responses that would provide insights into participants' subjective perceptions, encompassing their beliefs, thoughts, perspectives, viewpoints, and experiences. This approach is specifically designed to fulfil the need for triangulating data sources. The data was gathered from October 15, 2023, to February 20, 2024 from 341 respondents through sharing of the questionnaire links on various social media platforms using Google Forms (see Privara, 2024). The data collection period span to several months so that the data obtained would be diverse and contain information on changes in the examined variables. Based on the research objectives and questions, the main networks chosen for the dissemination of the links to the questionnaires included Instagram, Twitter, and email distribution. These platforms were selected because they allow reaching a large number of users and effectively set the focus on certain groups of a population. The use of social media to gather data has been promoted through its efficiency in reaching a large number of people within a short span, and with minimal costs (Bellet et al., 2022; Tsen and Cheng, 2021).

The sampling population of interest was comprised of persons above eighteen years of age who are active users of social media. The selection of this category rests with the presumption that every individual with social media page must have interacted with digital interfaces hence they would be ideal respondents for an online questionnaire. Convenience sampling method was used basically because of practicality and since participants could be easily accessed online. Convenience sampling is useful when the research seeks to collect data from a clearly available data source in the shortest time possible (Bellett al., 2022; Tsen & Cheng, 2021). The questionnaires were administered online, mainly via social media platforms

such as Instagram and Twitter and through emails, thereby providing the sample demography's variability.

The literature review identified six emerging issues that are relevant to DT, based on which primary data collection was used in the development of the questionnaire: Perceived Benefits (PB), Perceived Complexity (PC), Management Supports (MS), Information System Capacity (IC), Government Supports (GS), Competitive Pressures (CP). The DT will be a success only by identification and the purposeful utilization of these factors. All these factors are not adoption-only factors, but also will make the adoption competitive and resilience enough in the growing digital business environment. Organizations that can navigate these factors strategically are better poised to survive and thrive in the digital age. Thus, a set of questions for the questionnaire was developed with the intent of gathering the necessary data on the topic of the research, formulated based on previous literatures. To allow for extensive analysis, respondents were guided to answer the question using a Likert scale, the option most suitable for the assessment of attitudes and perceptions. Due to the sensitive nature of the study, the ethical considerations were a core component of the research process. The study employed only volunteer participants with the respondents given information about the specific study and its purpose. To ensure anonymity and privacy of the participants, data collection and analysis were conducted in a way that preserved participants' identities. However, convenience sampling has some practical advantage, it also has certain limitations. One of such limitation is that random sampling is not used, and thereby can be a source of bias. However, large sample size and respondents with various demographics background might help to mitigate this limitation. Thus, future research work could incorporate the random sampling techniques to increase the external validity of the study.

In the current study, with the view of identifying the relevant relationships, the PLS-SEM technique was applied. First, it is effective for working with large samples to overcome methodological problems such as non-normality (Hair et al., 2012, 2019; Nitzl, 2016). Additionally, the number of responses collected could be extensive, and thus the efficiency of PLS-SEM in handling large datasets play a critical role. Secondly, while using the PLS-SEM approach, the total system of equations is solved, and all the parameters of these equations have been estimated without carrying out independent estimations. This approach enables researchers to focus on the complexity of the association between the variables and obtain a better understanding of the nature of the constructs. Additionally, another strength of PLS-SEM is its capability to handle random error in the estimation process (Hayes et al., 2017). This aspect increases the reliability of the results, as it prevents the findings from being skewed by measurement error. The use of random measured error is essential where in survey-based research one has to be precise with measurements.

Lastly, it is necessary to emphasize that the choice of data collecting, the use of social networks as samples, the convenience-nonprobability sampling, and PLS-SEM as the analysis method can be considered as strengths of the study. Additionally, the application of various analytical tools and consideration of ethical factors ensure the relevancy and accuracy of the result.

4. Result

As presented in Table 1. Most of the respondents were over 36 years old (average 32 years) and were operating micro-enterprises with less than 10 employees. Their levels of education were mostly at high school or below, thus indicating a factor that might emerge as an area to be enhanced by education and developing relevant skills. As it can be seen from this demographic profile, this is a landscape overwhelmed by small-scale, owner-operated enterprises; improving education opportunities and support to business is likely to make a remarkable difference in terms of growth and sustainability. While the gross split by gender is relatively even, thus inclusive, the high percentage of micro businesses underlines that business growth for economic development needs targeted support. Thus, the organization and participant profiles support sample representativeness.

Table 1. Demographic and Business Statistics of the Respondents

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender			Type of Business¹		
Male	179	52.49%	Micro Business	258	75.66%
Female	162	47.51%	Small Business	50	14.66%
Age (in years)			Medium Business	33	9.68%
Less than 25	25	7.33%	Position in Business		
Between 26 - 30	31	9.09%	Owner	312	91.50%
Between 31 - 35	50	14.66%	Manager	29	8.50%
Between 36 - 40	56	16.42%	Number of Employees		
Between 41 - 45	83	24.34%	Less than 10	288	84.46%
More than 45	96	28.15%	Between 11 - 20	9	2.64%
Education			Between 11 - 20	9	21 - 30
Highschool & less	201	58.94%	Between 31 - 40	12	3.52%
Diploma	20	5.87%	Between 41 - 50	10	2.93%
Bachelor	101	29.62%	More than 50	15	4.40%
Postgraduate/Master	19	5.57%			
Number of Total Respondents				341	100 %

Source: Author Analysis Based on Survey data

Further, the study utilized the measurement model of PLS in order to test the reliability and validity of the constructs in the structural equation model. Specifically, the results affirm that all the constructs—PB, PC, MS, IC, GS, CP, and DT—possess significant psychometric properties. All the value of items loadings, specifically, are greater than 0.70, confirming good indicator reliability. Moreover, the values of VIF for all the items are below or near 3.3, thereby ruling out multicollinearity. Further, all Cronbach's alpha values for constructs fall within the acceptable range of 0.795 to 0.910, indicating good to excellent internal consistency. In addition, reliability ranges from 0.867 to 0.937, thereby showing further high reliability. Finally, the AVE is above 0.50 for all, thereby indicating adequate convergent validity. Together, these findings suggest that the measurement model is robust—that each construct is being measured with reliability and validity.² The detailed finding is presented in Table.2.

¹ Micro business = Max net assets IDR 50 million and max annual sales IDR 300 million

Small business = Net assets IDR 50 - 500 million and annual sales IDR 300 million - 2.5 billion

Medium business = Net assets > IDR 500 million and annual sales IDR 2.5 - 50 billion

² In the table, a construct is an abstract concept measured by a number of observed variables; these are called items. For instance, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Complexity, and DT. Each of the constructs is operationalized by items, for example PB-1 and PB-2. "Item loading" refers to the correlation of an item with its construct. High item loadings above 0.70 would suggest that items reliably measure their respective constructs.

Table 2. PLS Measurement Model Output

Construct	Item	Item loading	VIF	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	AVE
Perceived benefits (PB)	PB-1	0.896	2.881	0.889	0.922	0.749
	PB-2	0.897	2.715			
	PB-3	0.780	1.848			
	PB-4	0.883	2.538			
Perceived complexity (PC)	PC-1	0.752	1.500	0.795	0.867	0.619
	PC-2	0.786	1.648			
	PC-3	0.794	1.763			
	PC-4	0.814	1.728			
Management supports (MS)	MS-1	0.816	2.774	0.828	0.886	0.661
	MS-2	0.877	2.209			
	MS-3	0.816	1.927			
	MS-4	0.736	1.701			
IS capacity (IC)	IC-1	0.876	2.546	0.910	0.937	0.788
	IC-2	0.889	2.791			
	IC-3	0.909	1.181			
	IC-4	0.875	2.601			
Government supports (GS)	GS-1	0.839	2.995	0.907	0.934	0.779
	GS-2	0.923	1.901			
	GS-3	0.894	2.293			
	GS-4	0.873	1.868			
Competitive pressures (CP)	CP-1	0.739	1.677	0.854	0.901	0.696
	CP-2	0.854	2.294			
	CP-3	0.884	2.610			
	CP-4	0.852	2.195			
Digital transformation (DT)	DT-1	0.879	2.811	0.889	0.923	0.751
	DT-2	0.920	1.585			
	DT-3	0.835	2.202			
	DT-4	0.829	2.019			

Source: Author Analysis Based on Survey data

Additionally, based on the examination of the discriminant validity by the Fornell-Larcker criterion as presented in Table 3., we can infer that the constructs in the model have satisfactory discriminant validity.³ In fact, the square root of the average variance extracted for each construct is higher compared to its correlations with other constructs. Accordingly, the data supports the discriminant validity of the constructs, thereby confirming that they are distinct from one another and appropriate for further structural analysis in hypothesis testing. This strengthens the validity of any conclusions drawn from subsequent analyses of these constructs.

³ The Fornell-Larcker criterion is one of the tests that assesses the construct discriminant validity in a model. Discriminant validity ensures that a construct is really distinct from other constructs by contrasting the square root of the average variance extracted of each construct to the correlations between that construct and others. In the table below, diagonal elements (in bold) capture the square root of the AVE for each construct, and off-diagonal elements capture the correlation of constructs.

Table 3. Discriminant Validity of Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

	CP	DT	GS	IC	MS	PB	PC
CP	0.834						
DT	0.740	0.866					
GS	0.400	0.441	0.883				
IC	0.628	0.700	0.413	0.888			
MS	0.629	0.688	0.386	0.731	0.813		
PB	0.441	0.519	0.338	0.490	0.702	0.865	
PC	0.438	0.412	0.296	0.493	0.511	0.421	0.787

Source: Author Analysis Based on Survey data

Further, Table 4. Present the the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) test for further investigation of the discriminant validity of our contract.⁴ It is observed that the HTMT ratio calculation shows good discriminant validity for all constructs; in fact, all ratios fall below the threshold of 0.85, proving that the constructs are truly different from one another. This could be subject to one exception: the pair MS-IC, whose HTMT ratio was 0.849, precisely at the threshold, which may indicate it would call for closer examination. The overall fit indices provide evidence that the constructs specified in this research are both well-defined and differentiated, hence it supports a robust measurement model.

Table 4. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio

	CP	DT	GS	IC	MS	PB	PC
CP							
DT	0.837						
GS	0.433	0.472					
IC	0.708	0.776	0.436				
MS	0.741	0.797	0.431	0.849			
PB	0.485	0.572	0.369	0.540	0.811		
PC	0.533	0.491	0.350	0.579	0.635	0.515	

Source: Author Analysis Based on Survey data

Table 5. provide the results of a structural model, investigating the impact of various factors on DT. The results of structural modeling show that IS capacity and competitive pressure are highly significant drivers of DT, with p-values way below 0.01. Government support was also very important, with $p < 0.05$. The management support was marginally significant; $p = 0.052$, which means it could have some effects, although weaker compared with the other significant drivers. Moreover, perceived benefit and perceived complexity do not have a significant influence on DT, as indicated by their high p-values of 0.182 and 0.369, respectively. The model explains 67% of the variance for DT, concluding it fits and is predictive in relevance with $Q^2 = 0.643$. These results underline the paramount roles of IS capacity, competitive pressure, and government support for DT, while perceived benefits and complexity are not that powerful.

⁴ The Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio is a measurement method to evaluate the discriminant validity between the constructs in structural equation modelling, concerned with ensuring that the respective constructs are related to different concepts. In general, an HTMT ratio below 0.85 (or sometimes 0.90) is considered acceptable for good discriminant validity.

Table 5. Structural Model Results

Hypothesis	Structural path	T statistics	p value
H1	Perceived benefits	1.335	0.182
H2	Perceived complexity	0.889	0.369
H3	Management supports	1.946	0.052
H4	IS capacity	3.556**	0.000
H5	Government support	2.249*	0.025
H6	Competitive pressure	6.139**	0.000
R ²			0.670
Adjusted R ²			0.664
Q ²			0.643
Number of Observations			341

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two tailed)

Source: Author Analysis Based on Survey data

Table 6. presents a summary of results derived from the structural model adopted to investigate the relationships among the different factors and DT in MSMEs. The influence of many factors on DT differs greatly between micro, small, and medium businesses. For instance, for micro businesses, competitive pressure, government support, and IS capacity are really important drivers, indicating the importance of external pressures and capabilities in terms of technology. For small businesses, paramount is the role of management support and IS capacity; thus, there must be proper managerial direction and IS infrastructure in place for DT. In the case of medium enterprises, however, none of the variables analysed appeared to play a major role, suggesting there may be other variables that might be relevant. Thus, external pressures and supporting mechanisms are critical to the micro-enterprises, and strong internal management and technology infrastructure are more important in small businesses, the medium businesses should obviously need to explore some other major drivers for the DT.

Table 6. Structural Model Results by MSMEs

Relationships with DT	Micro Business		Small Business		Medium Business	
	T statistics	p value	T statistics	p value	T statistics	p value
Perceived benefits	0.644	0.520	0.312	0.755	0.522	0.602
Perceived complexity	0.350	0.727	0.734	0.463	0.203	0.840
Management supports	1.698	0.089	2.237*	0.025	1.744	0.082
IS capacity	2.374*	0.018	3.675**	0.000	0.234	0.815
Government support	3.072**	0.002	0.189	0.850	0.496	0.620
Competitive pressure	6.809**	0.000	1.226	0.220	0.174	0.862
Number of Observations						341

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two tailed)

Source: Author Analysis Based on Survey data

5. Discussion

The aim of this research is to establish the determining factors of DT in MSMEs in Indonesia under post-pandemic environment. The need to understand the effect of competitive pressure, managerial support, IS capacity, government support, perceived benefits, and perceived complexity on the DT process justified the research.

The results underscore how crucial IS capacity, competitive pressure, and government support mark as significant enablers to DT, though relevant past literature emphasizes the condition of a strong IS structure "to enable a smooth integration of digital technologies" (Benbir-Ziv & Luftman, 2022). And competitive pressure illustrates the granularity within the market environment of the MSMEs that they need to be constantly innovating (Matt and Rauch, 2020). As Latianingsih et al. (2022) indicates, this enables the digital transition—by means of policies and incentives—needed in overcoming the regulatory and financial challenges that characterize progressive environment for MSMEs. Not remarkably, perceived benefits and perceived complexity did not significantly influence DT, suggesting that even though such factors are indeed essential, they may not define DT at the very core of the Indonesian MSMEs. This contrasts with some other previous studies in which perceived benefits were a major motivator for adoption (Straková et al., 2022). There are many potentials, but for Indonesian MSMEs, the immediacies of pressure and tangible support matter more than the benefits of—or complexity in—DT.

The study also found that influence of DT drivers, differs across enterprises of different sizes. For instance, for micro-enterprises, it involves external pressures and technological capabilities. This explain that the smaller the business, the more it reacts to external forces with the intensity to implement, sourcing from the technology. In the case of small business enterprises, it is internal management support and IS capacity, which shows that a firm should sail through this journey of DT, it requires strong leadership driven by robust technological frameworks. In medium enterprises, the analysed factors do not show significant influence on the dependent variable and may be driven by other factors, probably more strategic or resource intensive. The identified challenges of insufficient digital skills, lack of financial resources, and resistance to change with these principal barriers, raised in the reviewed existing literature (Rupeika-Apoga & Petrovska, 2022). To overcome these challenges, strategies of enhancing digital literacy, raising of funds and nurturing innovation culture in various organizations is essential. This is in addition to an enabling regulatory framework and incentives provided by the government.

The findings also underline tremendous opportunities for MSMEs, but enhanced capacity of information systems and support from governments equip business with competitiveness, businesses innovation, as well as adaption to market demands. Moreover, the educational gap—by filling it up with skill development—may be helpful to the owner and employees in order to widen the scope of online tools, hence motivating business growth and sustainability.

5. Conclusion

The paper contributes to the understanding of DT within Indonesian MSMEs by identifying key drivers and exploring their differential impact on various business sizes. The significant roles of IS capacity, competitive pressure, and government support, underline the fact that DT is a complex phenomenon, thus embrace technological readiness, external pressures, and supportive policies. It also determined that continuous support from the government in terms of favourable policies and financial incentives remains a very vital factor in facilitating DT in MSMEs. Digital infrastructures and targeted support can help overcome some of the most important barriers. The study also suggests that micro and small business enterprise business owners and managers alike should build more IS capacity and ensure strong support from the top of the managerial hierarchy. Therefore, these firms should take advantage of both available government support and market pressures, driving DT. Further, tailored educational programs by Educational Institutions to address skill gaps will prepare the workforce to enable them with needed digital competencies and, in turn, help the DT agenda at large.

However, the current study gives a fair understanding of the problem at hand, strategic and resource-intensive factors in DT among medium-sized enterprises should be analysed because the variables considered in the current study were not found to have a significant impact. Generalizability might also be ensured if random sampling techniques are applied to future studies. Thus, the study shows that DT is not an alternative but a necessity for successful MSMEs in Indonesia. Basically, by addressing the challenges identified and through focus on some of the remaining key drivers, such as capacity of IS, pressure from competition, and support from Government, MSMEs could enhance their competitiveness, resilience, and sustainability in a digital age.

Acknowledgements: The publication was co-financed by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1); Project number: 101086381; Project title: Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia.

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